

Patient and Clinic-Related Predictors of Inconsistent Antenatal Care use among Women Attending Care in Awka, South-East Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Background: The World Health Organization (WHO) recommends a minimum of eight antenatal clinic visits for safe motherhood. However, women in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) often miss one or more appointments, elevating their risk for adverse pregnancy outcomes. **Objectives:** The study is aimed at identifying the predictors of missed antenatal appointments among Nigerian women. **Methodology:** This study surveyed women receiving antenatal care at three hospitals in Southeastern Nigeria between March 2023 and May 2023, using a validated 25-item, well-structured, self-administered questionnaire. Out of the 400 distributed questionnaires, we retrieved 301. **Results:** Out of the 301 women surveyed, 115(35%) of them, said that they had missed at least one visit. In the bivariate and multivariate analyses, inconsistent antenatal care use was found to be significantly associated with factors such as advanced age, previous childbirth, higher educational attainment of the partner, receiving care at a government-owned hospital, high registration costs, unfavourable administrative policies, and unsatisfactory attitude of healthcare providers. **Conclusion:** Pregnancy outcomes remain relatively poor in SSA. This highlights the importance of inter-sectorial collaboration between ministries and stakeholders in developing overarching policies that would promote easy, accessible and affordable antenatal care services in SSA.

Keywords: Antenatal care; Pregnant women; Antenatal clinic.

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INTRODUCTION

Maternal mortality remains a central global health issue, with about 800 women dying daily from pregnancy-related complications across the world.¹ In the late 20th century, the International Health Community, which included the World Bank, World Health Organization (WHO), United Nations Population Fund, and agencies in multiple low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), launched the "Safe Motherhood Initiative" to combat the surging maternal mortality across LMICs.² One of the pillars of this initiative was the provision and adequate utilisation of antenatal care (ANC). Currently, WHO prescribes a minimum of eight antenatal visits to adequately prepare for delivery and avoid birth complications.³ This recommendation notwithstanding, many pregnant women in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) still struggle to meet up with the former minimum of four contacts.⁴ Recent data indicate that the percentage of women having at least four ANC visits varies considerably globally, ranging from an average of about 55% across SSA to over 95% across Europe and North America.⁵ Given the morbidity associated with inadequate ANC, it is important to identify factors associated with this phenomenon among women in SSA.

Prior studies on exploring ANC use generally focus on the sociodemographic characteristics of the women, neglecting the features of the antenatal clinics and healthcare professionals that provide these services but less evidence exists on the factors that predict inconsistent ANC use among registered women.^{1,6} This limitation applies especially to studies using secondary data from the Demographic and Health Survey (DHS), which only collect information about the women.^{1,7,8} However, the characteristics of the ANC clinics and healthcare providers can significantly influence the consistency of women's use of antenatal care, beyond their own sociodemographic characteristics.

This research sets out to address this knowledge gap by conducting a primary study among pregnant women in southeastern Nigeria, the most populous

country in Africa. Like most SSA countries, Nigeria offers healthcare through two main categories of providers: public or government-funded facilities and private facilities, which can be either for-profit or non-profit (usually faith-based or "mission") facilities.⁹ While public facilities are generally more accessible and affordable in low-income settings, women in SSA have indicated a preference for obtaining obstetric services at private facilities for a variety of reasons, including empathy and availability of doctors, convenience, privacy, promptness, continuity of care, perceived service quality, and a symbol of status.^{9,10} Nonetheless, women in SSA countries continue to widely use both public and private clinics.

Thus, using data from women obtaining ANC services at selected public and private Nigerian hospitals, the study aimed to evaluate the factors associated with the inconsistent use of antenatal care in the SSA context. These could include characteristics of the women (including sociodemographic and obstetric features), as well as characteristics of the clinics and healthcare professionals providing them with antenatal care. The results of this study would guide efforts to identify women at a higher risk of missing ANC appointments, thereby improving pregnancy outcomes across the region.

METHODOLOGY

Study Design

This retrospective cross-sectional study was conducted between March 2023 and May 2023 to evaluate the factors associated with the utilization of antenatal care in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Study Settings

This study was conducted in three hospitals in Awka, the capital city of Anambra State. The hospitals include Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University Teaching Hospital (COOUTH), Regina Caeli Specialist Hospital (RCSHA), and Izunna Hospital and Maternity, Awka (IHMA). COOUTH

is the state-owned tertiary hospital; RCSHA is a mission hospital; and Izunna Hospital & Maternity is privately owned.

Ethical Committee Approval

Approval was sought from the Health Research and Ethics Committee (HREC) of the Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University Teaching Hospital (COOUTH) Amaku, Awka before the commencement of the study. The administrators of the three hospitals were duly informed about the study protocol and it was approved by them.

Eligibility Criteria

All the pregnant women who were accessing antenatal care from the aforementioned hospitals and were willing to participate in the study were recruited.

Sample size and selection

A total population of 1320 pregnant women were expected within four weeks of antenatal visits in the three hospitals (COOUTH: 600, RCSHA: 600, IHMA: 120). The minimum sample size of 298 was calculated using the Raosoft® Sample Size Calculator, assuming a 5% margin of error, a 95% confidence level, and a 50% response distribution²⁰. The sample consisted of pregnant women who were willing to participate in the study and received antenatal care from the aforementioned hospitals. Those that were not willing to participate or absent from the clinic during data collection process were excluded.

Data collection

The objectives of the study were explained to the participants with oral or written consent obtained from those who agreed to participate. Confidentiality was maintained as the names of the participants were not requested. The study instrument is a 25-item structured, self-administered questionnaire in three domains. The first domain focused on socio-demographic details. The second domain seek to provide answers to the factors affecting the choice or

attendance at an antenatal clinic. The third domain comprises indices to evaluate satisfaction with the antenatal clinic.

Instrument Validity

We validated the questionnaire by assessing three central components of survey instrument validity: face validity, content validity, and internal consistency.¹¹ Face and content validity assessments usually involve a qualitative assessment of the survey instrument by experts, to ensure that it is measuring what it was intended to measure, in all important domains.¹¹ This was conducted by two clinicians on the research team and a small subset of the study participants, during the iterative questionnaire development process. For internal consistency, we computed Cronbach's alpha statistic assessing the agreement between items in the survey measuring satisfaction with ANC services and professionals. We obtained a Cronbach's alpha of 0.81 (95% confidence interval (CI): 0.78 to 0.84), suggesting that the questionnaire items are likely measuring the same underlying concept, and indicating the validity of our instrument.¹¹

Data Analysis

Data was analysed using IBM SPSS Version 25.0 (IBM Corp., Version 25.0, Armonk, NY, USA). Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the data, while Pearson's Chi-Square was used to test the association between variables, with statistical significance set at $P < 0.05$.

RESULTS

A total of 301 women filled out the questionnaires: 134 from COOUTH, 132 from RCSHA, and 35 from IHMA. Of these, 115 (38.2%) missed at least one prior appointment during the current pregnancy, while 186 (61.8%) did not miss any antenatal appointments. The pie chart (**Figure 1**) shows the proportions of women who missed none, or one or more appointments during their current pregnancy.

Figure 1: Pie chart showing proportions of women who missed none, or one or more antenatal clinic

appointments during their current pregnancy at the time of survey

Bivariate Analyses

Table I shows the crude associations of the maternal factors with *any* missed appointments. Although not statistically significant, older women were more likely than younger women to miss antenatal appointments. Regarding women's parity, respondents with one or two previous live births were significantly more likely to miss antenatal appointments during the current pregnancy than first-time mothers (OR: 2.38, 95% CI: 1.39, 4.12, $p = 0.006$).

Table II shows similar crude associations for clinic-related and healthcare professional-related factors that could influence women's consistency with their antenatal clinic appointments. Firstly, women attending government hospitals were about three times more likely to miss their appointments than those receiving care at private for-profit hospitals (OR: 3.15, 95% CI: 1.35 to 8.28, $p = 0.03$). Similarly, women who perceived the antenatal care

services as "costly" were about twice as likely to miss their appointments (OR: 1.98, 95% CI: 1.22 to 3.23, $p = 0.006$). Importantly, women who reported dissatisfaction with hospital administrative policies were over twice as likely to miss appointments as those who did not (OR: 2.61, 95% CI: 1.62 to 4.23, $p < 0.001$).

Furthermore, healthcare professionals' attitudes toward women showed an association with their adherence to scheduled ANC clinic appointments. Women who were dissatisfied with their doctor's attitude towards them were almost twice as likely to miss appointments as those who reported being satisfied (OR: 1.86, 95% CI: 0.98 to 3.54, $p = 0.04$). Similarly, but less importantly, women who reported dissatisfaction with their nurses' attitude towards them were 21% more likely to miss antenatal clinic appointments (OR: 1.21, 95% CI: 0.71, 2.04, $p = 0.50$) than those who were satisfied.

Multivariable Analysis

We attempted to build a parsimonious multivariable prediction model, including the most important predictors of missed appointments among women in our study population. This could guide efforts among healthcare providers to identify at-risk women and follow them closely.

Table III shows the variables included in this model after a backward, stepwise selection process. The p -value for the Hosmer-Lemeshow goodness of fit (GOF) test is 0.205, suggesting that the model fits the data well. Similarly, the c-statistic of the area under the operating characteristic curve (AUC) is 0.714, suggesting a good predictive value for the model. This means that, given the included variables, the final model can correctly discriminate between women who missed or did not miss antenatal clinic appointments 71.4% of the time.

Table I: Sociodemographic and obstetric characteristics of women who missed or did not miss any antenatal clinic appointments at three hospitals in Anambra, Nigeria.

Characteristic	Missed any visit n=115 (%)	No missed visits n=186 (%)	Crude odds ratio (95% CI)	P-value
<i>Sociodemographic</i>				
Age (years)				0.7
<20	1 (20%)	4 (80%)	1.00 (ref)	
20-35	107 (38%)	173 (62%)	2.47 (0.36, 48.7)	
>35	7 (44%)	9 (56%)	3.11 (0.35, 68.5)	
Marital status				0.9
Married	111 (38%)	180 (62%)	1.00 (ref)	
Not married	4 (40%)	6 (60%)	1.08 (0.27, 3.87)	
Ethnicity				0.05
Igbo	112 (40%)	171 (60%)	1.00 (ref)	
Yoruba	2 (50%)	2 (50%)	1.53 (0.18, 12.9)	
Hausa	0 (0%)	1 (100%)	0.00	
Other	1 (7.7%)	12 (92%)	0.13 (0.01, 0.66)	
Religion				0.4
Christian	114 (39%)	181 (61%)	1.00 (ref)	
Muslim	1 (17%)	5 (83%)	0.32 (0.02, 2.00)	
Education				0.9
Primary	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	-	
Secondary	37 (38%)	60 (62%)	1.00 (ref)	
Tertiary	78 (38%)	126 (62%)	1.00 (0.61, 1.66)	
Partner's Education				0.007
Primary	2 (8.7%)	21 (91%)	1.00 (ref)	
Secondary	28 (36%)	49 (64%)	6.00 (1.60, 39.3)	
Tertiary	85 (42%)	116 (58%)	7.69 (2.18, 48.9)	
Employment				0.5
Employed	89 (37%)	150 (63%)	1.00 (ref)	
Unemployed	26 (42%)	36 (58%)	1.22 (0.68, 2.14)	
<i>Obstetric</i>				
Live Births				0.006
None	31 (28%)	81 (72%)	1.00 (ref)	
1-2	61 (48%)	67 (52%)	2.38 (1.39, 4.12)	
>2	18 (36%)	32 (64%)	1.47 (0.72, 2.98)	

Table II: Clinic-related and healthcare professional-related factors associated with women's compliance with scheduled antenatal clinic appointments at three hospitals in Anambra, Nigeria

Characteristic	Missed any visit n=115 (%)	No missed visits n=186 (%)	Crude odds ratio (95% CI)	P-value
<i>Clinic-related factors</i>				
Clinic Ownership				0.032
Private – For Profit	7 (20%)	28 (80%)	1.00 (ref)	
Private – Mission	49 (37%)	83 (63%)	2.36 (1.01, 6.24)	
Government	59 (44%)	75 (56%)	3.15 (1.35, 8.28)	
Registration Cost				0.006
Satisfactory	37 (29%)	90 (71%)	1.00 (ref)	
Unsatisfactory	78 (45%)	96 (55%)	1.98 (1.22, 3.23)	
Distance				0.15
Close	49 (34%)	95 (66%)	1.00 (ref)	
Far	66 (42%)	91 (58%)	1.41 (0.88, 2.25)	
Waiting Time				0.09
Satisfactory	48 (33%)	96 (67%)	1.00 (ref)	
Unsatisfactory	67 (43%)	90 (57%)	1.50 (0.93, 2.39)	
Hospital Policies				<0.001
Satisfactory	52 (29%)	127 (71%)	1.00 (ref)	
Unsatisfactory	63 (52%)	59 (48%)	2.61 (1.62, 4.23)	
Hospital Amenities				0.6
Satisfactory	80 (37%)	135 (63%)	1.00 (ref)	
Unsatisfactory	35 (41%)	51 (59%)	1.16 (0.69, 1.93)	
Ease of Getting Medication				0.02
Satisfactory	66 (34%)	131 (66%)	1.00 (ref)	
Unsatisfactory	49 (47%)	55 (53%)	1.77 (1.09, 2.88)	
<i>Healthcare Professional-related factors</i>				
Physician Attitude				0.04
Satisfactory	92 (36%)	164 (64%)	1.00 (ref)	

Unsatisfactory Nurse Attitude	23 (51%)	22 (49%)	1.86 (0.98, 3.54)	0.50
Satisfactory	83 (37%)	141 (63%)	1.00 (ref)	
Unsatisfactory	32 (42%)	45 (58%)	1.21 (0.71, 2.04)	

Table III: Important predictors of missed antenatal appointments from the parsimonious multivariable prediction model

Characteristic	Odds ratio	95% CI	P-value
<i>Maternal Characteristics</i>			
Live Births			
None	1.00 (ref)		
1-2	1.86	1.04, 3.37	0.038
>2	1.37	0.63, 2.93	0.40
Partner's Education			
Primary	1.00 (ref)		
Secondary	8.27	1.94, 58.3	0.01
Tertiary	11.1	2.79, 75.3	0.003
<i>Clinic-related factors</i>			
Clinic Ownership			
Private – For Profit	1.00 (ref)		
Private – Mission	1.94	0.77, 5.40	0.18
Government	1.97	0.78, 5.45	0.17
Hospital Policies			
Satisfactory	1.00 (ref)		
Unsatisfactory	2.04	1.11, 3.76	0.02
Registration Cost			
Satisfactory	1.00 (ref)		
Unsatisfactory	1.26	0.70, 2.25	0.44
Physician Attitude			
Satisfactory	1.00 (ref)		
Unsatisfactory	1.89	0.85, 4.30	0.12

NB: "ref" = reference level; Model AUC c-statistic = 0.714

DISCUSSION

Maternal and neonatal mortality remains a central public health issue globally, especially in developing countries. The WHO estimated in 2024 that 1 in 49 women in low-income countries will die from a maternal cause, compared to 1 in 5300 for high-income countries.¹² To address this challenge, the community of nations set a Sustainable Development Goal (SDG 3) of reducing the global maternal mortality ratio (MMR) to less than 70 per 100 000 births by the year 2030, with no country having a maternal mortality rate of more than twice the global average.¹³

The significance of maternal age agrees with the existing literature, which associates younger

maternal age with increased odds of ANC utilization.^{7,14} This is likely related to the inverse association observed between women's parity and their ANC use consistency. In a study using Demographic and Health Survey (DHS) data from Northern Nigeria, a negative dose-response relationship was reported between a woman's number of previous pregnancies and her likelihood of attending ANC visits in her current pregnancy.⁷ Similarly, a recent study using DHS data for over 56,000 women across nine SSA countries reported that women in their first-time pregnancy had significantly higher odds of attending fewer than four ANC visits across all countries. As an explanation for this observation, older pregnant women probably rely on the knowledge and experience gained from their previous pregnancies,

making them more likely to miss ANC appointments than younger women in their first pregnancies.

It was observed that no significant association existed between women's education and their tendency to miss ANC appointments. This may be because our study was conducted in an urban setting and all the participating women had at least secondary-level education. This contrasts with previous studies from SSA, where 20% to 80% of the surveyed pregnant women had no formal education.^{7,8,14} Thus, it is possible that the largely uniform educational attainment among women in our study population had no significant association with ANC use consistency. It was further observed that women whose partners had higher education were more likely to miss antenatal appointments, even after adjusting for other factors in the multivariable model. This contradicts the results of other studies which associated higher ANC use with greater educational attainment of women's partners.^{15,16,17} The intricate interplay between women's and their partners' educational attainment, and how these relate to ANC utilization, represents an area for further research – particularly in contexts like ours, where women are generally well-educated.

Our study also showed that women who received care at the government-owned hospitals were three times as likely to miss ANC appointments as their counterparts at private hospitals. This preference for private hospitals has been well-recorded in LMIC contexts. For instance, studies reported that women in Southwestern Nigeria preferred to patronize private clinics due to convenience, privacy, shorter waiting times, and its indication of high socioeconomic status.¹⁰ They also studied the choice of healthcare facilities among pregnant women in Lagos, Nigeria, reporting a greater use of private clinics due to better service quality, availability of skilled healthcare staff, clean environment, and positive staff attitude.¹⁸ Similarly, another study from Ghana showed that, while private hospitals charged more money for the same services, patients were more satisfied with their services than those provided by public hospitals.¹⁹

This preference of private over publicly owned clinics may be explained by other clinic characteristics which were also associated with women's adherence to their ANC appointments in our study. Specifically, missing ANC appointments was directly associated with unfavourable administrative policies, long waiting times, high registration costs, difficulty obtaining medications, and the clinic's remoteness to the woman's home. In addition, negative attitude of the healthcare professionals was also positively associated with missed ANC appointments. This corresponds with the results of similar studies conducted across LMICs, where ANC use was impeded by greater distance from the clinic, high cost of services, and poor service from healthcare professionals.^{17,18}

This study has several strengths, including its relative novelty of identifying clinic-related predictors of inconsistent antenatal care (ANC) use in a sub-Saharan African context, addressing a critical public health issue in the region. The use of a validated structured questionnaire allowed for the collection of detailed and relevant data. Additionally, our relatively high response rate (75.3%) enhances the reliability of the findings. However, the study also has important limitations. Firstly, its cross-sectional design precludes establishing causality between identified predictors and inconsistent ANC use. Secondly, the study did not explore other possible barriers, such as cultural or psychosocial factors, which might also influence ANC attendance. Finally, the study sample was limited to women attending three hospitals in Southeastern Nigeria, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other regions or populations.

CONCLUSION

Our study has identified a range of factors that may contribute to inconsistent ANC use among women in SSA. The evidence suggests that women would increase their use of ANC services if hospital policies and the attitudes of healthcare providers are more favorable to them. Thus, as a vital part of the efforts to improve maternal outcomes globally, ANC

clinics have the responsibility of creating administrative policies and clinic environments that are favourable to their clients. In addition, governments across SSA should aim to provide free or subsidized ANC services to pregnant women; and where possible, provisions should be made to transport women to their ANC clinics are no or reduced costs. In summary, our study highlights the importance of inter-sectorial collaboration between ministries and stakeholders in developing overarching policies that would promote easy, accessible and affordable ANC services in SSA.

Conflict of statement

The authors declared no conflict of interests.

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Authors roles

Author PIO and EJU conceptualized the idea and designed the study tools. The results were analyzed by author SCO. Author LEO, MAO, and OHU were involved in the data collection while author KCA supervised the study. All the authors were involved in writing the manuscript. The final version of the manuscript was read and approved by all the authors for publication.

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